

The protein interactome topography of Clathrin-mediated endocytosis

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Abstract

Clathrin mediated endocytosis (CME) is a highly conserved Eukaryotic process allowing for the regulated uptake of material from the extracellular space into the cytoplasm. It is critical for a wide range of cell functions, and dependent upon specific protein-protein interactions to allow for the precise identification and carriage of cargo across the plasma membrane. To gain both a deeper and wider understanding of the organisation of CME in mammalian cells, in this study the protein interactomes for conserved components of the human CME machinery were collated and assembled into a comprehensive network for this process. This network was then subjected to cluster-based analysis and weighted according to tissue expression, providing insights into the pathways regulating CME and how this process varies across human tissues. Finally, the overlap between the CME interactome and a monogenic human neurodegenerative disorders was assessed, illustrating the utility of this approach to understand both physiological and pathophysiological events.

Key Words

Clathrin mediated endocytosis, protein interactome, endocytosis, vesicle trafficking

1.0 Introduction

Endocytosis - the ability to move material from the extracellular space into the cytoplasm - is a fundamental property of life. The Eukarya have evolved a sophisticated array of complementary and parallel regulated endocytic pathways, allowing for specific and controlled endocytosis responding to the external environment and intracellular prompts (Doherty and McMahon 2009). Clathrin mediated endocytosis (CME) is a specialised form of endocytosis, allowing for receptor mediated uptake of targeted cargo, and is defined by the formation of a geodesic clathrin cage around vesicles evaginated from the plasma membrane, which are then uncoated to release cargo (Kaksonen and Roux 2018). The precise regulation of CME is dependent upon a wide range of macromolecular interactions, between cargo and receptors, clathrin and its adaptors, and between proteins and other cellular components. Mapping, defining, and characterising these interactions provides both important insights into the architecture and events that define CME in different organisms, tissues and cells, as well as providing a framework for modulating CME in disease. While systematic cataloguing and categorisation of the components of CME has previously been carried out using gene ontology as a framework (Croft et al. 2011), exemplified by a framework for autophagy (Varusai et al. 2021), establishing a comprehensive map for the interactions between the components of CME has not been attempted to date. The increasing volume and quality of data relating to protein-protein interactions, driven partly by advances in analytical technology, provides an opportunity to develop large scale maps of biological processes, facilitating sophisticated topological analysis of these networks to provide insights into the underlying biological pathways. In this study, the core protein components of the CME machinery in human cells has been used as a framework to construct a protein interactome for this process. This allowed for weighted topological analysis of variation in CME across tissues, as well as the identification of clusters in the pathways regulating CME, and overlap with pathological processes – using the example of neurodegenerative disorders.

2.0 Results

To create a comprehensive map for the process of CME in human cells, the Reactome annotated proteins for CME were identified and categorised using a simplified staging framework for the process (figure 1A). A total of 143 proteins were derived from Reactome (see supplemental table 1), with each allocated to stages based upon the Reactome categorisation (figure 1B). 85 of the seed proteins were associated with every stage of CME, 31 associated with three stages, 3 associated with 2 stages, and the remainder (24) displaying unique association with 1 stage alone (figure 1C). Using protein-protein interaction (PPI) data collated from multiple repositories, a PPI network was constructed from these seed proteins (displayed in figure 2). This revealed a highly complex, and deeply interconnected, overall schema for CME.

To investigate the connectedness of this network, the distribution and degrees of relationship across the interactome were assessed (figure 3). This highlighted that the majority of proteins were connected by a small number of interactions, and that a large proportion of connectedness was dependent upon a small number of highly interlinked proteins hubs. The bulk of interactions were common across the five stages of CME, however each stage had a number of unique interactions, displayed in figure 4.

A greedy clustering algorithm was applied to identify topological clusters within the network for each stage. This identified a number of tightly interconnected clusters within the network, highlighting specific protein clusters/complexes found at different stages of CME (summarised in figure 5 and supplemental tables 2 and 3). A more detailed projection of these clusters is shown in figure 6, showing individual components of each of these – with the clusters identified in stage 4 and stage 5 being identical. Notably, the COP9 signalosome was enriched and clustered with the first stage of CME. The COP9 signalosome has previously been reported to use clathrin coated vesicles as a scaffold for assembly, supporting the validity of this clustering approach (Schulze-Niemand and Naumann 2023). An ontological analysis of these clusters is displayed in figure 7, highlighting key cellular processes associated with each of these clusters. As expected, cellular import and clathrin mediated endocytosis are prominent, however multiple additional terms were highlighted – indicating the contribution and utility of CME and clathrin coated vesicles across a wider range of cellular processes.

In order to assess how the protein interactome for CME varies across specific human tissues, transcript levels of its protein components were compared across 12 anatomically distinct human nervous system tissues derived from the GTEx dataset (Consortium 2013). Hierarchical clustering revealed a predominantly consistent expression pattern across the human nervous system (figure 8C). Weighted gene co-expression network analysis (WGCNA) identified one co-expression module was identified in the nervous system across the network (figure 8A). This module (module eigengene, ME), consisting of 30 seed proteins, was then subjected to a module-trait analysis across the 12 sampled tissues, revealing distinct patterns of expression for these genes (figure 8B). Expression of the ME was positively correlated with the frontal cortex (region BA9) ($r = 0.288$).

Finally, the overlaps between the CME protein network and proteins involved in neurodegenerative disease were examined to understand and contextualise disease

biology. To achieve this, a catalogue of neurodegenerative disease associated proteins was established, focusing on validated monogenic forms of disease. This was derived from the PanelApp resource, which annotates clinically established forms of inherited disease (Martin et al. 2019) (figure 9A). These were then overlapped with the established CME network, and segregated according to the five stages of CME (figure 9B-F). To assess whether these disease specific networks were altered across central nervous system tissues, the hierarchical analysis of co-expression and DGE analysis were repeated, centred on neurodegenerative genes (figure 10A and 10B respectively), revealing distinct patterns and arrangements of monogenic proteins associated with neurodegenerative disease and CME.

3.0 Discussion

CME is a valuable exemplar for the complex organisation and regulation of core cellular processes in Eukaryotic cells. In this study, a multi-omic strategy was adopted to map and characterise the PPI networks and pathways underlying CME in human tissues. The overall topology of this network reinforces the concept of CME as a multifaceted and extensive web of interactions providing for specific and constrained uptake events. Clustering analysis revealed previously described functional complexes that intersect with CME (for example the COP9 signalosome), as well as novel putative pathways.

To examine tissue-specific variation in CME pathways, we compared expression and co-expression patterns of network components across 12 healthy human tissues. This revealed a predominantly uniform expression of core genes across the network and across brain regions, likely driven by the conserved nature of CME. The tibial nerve, however, displayed a distinct pattern of expression – suggesting that the demands of the peripheral nervous system diverge from those of the central nervous system.

There are a number of neurodegenerative disorders with clear and robust links to CME, most notably Parkinson's and parkinsonism where mutations in a number of genes (as well as common variation) contribute to disease risk (Kaci 2026). In order to investigate the overlap between CME and neurodegenerative disorders, the CME network was compared to a curated list of monogenic form of neurodegenerative diseases. This provides a formal framework for understanding the interplay between the physiological process of CME, and the pathophysiological processes involved in the death of neurons in the central nervous system, and again highlights the utility of a network based approach.

While a network based approach provides a powerful set of tools for defining and dissecting complex cellular processes, there are important caveats to using this method. First, a key limitation of PPI network analysis is that it depends heavily on the current state of the knowledge. In the case of CME, there are substantial gaps in our knowledge of the protein repertoire, which may lead to under-representation of certain CMR components or sub-pathways. Second, expression and co-expression analyses in this study were based on transcriptomics data, which do not account for protein stability or post-transcriptional regulation and modifications. However, since no large-scale, tissue-resolved human proteomics resource is yet available, these regulatory layers could not be incorporated into the present study.

In summary, this study provides the first systematic derivation of the CME protein interactome and highlights key network modules, tissue-specific features, and points of intersection with neurodegenerative disease. These analyses identify several candidate pathways and complexes for future functional validation. In future work, this framework can be expanded as additional CME components and interactions are identified, allowing the network to become more comprehensive. As bulk-tissue and single-cell proteomic resources grow, these data will enable refinement of the network at the protein level and provide higher-resolution insight into CME regulation. In parallel, extending expression-based comparisons to peripheral tissues will help define how CME varies across the body and how these differences relate to a broader spectrum of disease.

4.0 Materials and methods

CME annotation and stages

The CME seed proteins and stages in humans were derived from the online data repository Reactome (Gillespie et al. 2022; Fabregat et al. 2018) (accessed Oct 2021) via a query for “Clathrin-Mediated Endocytosis” (Rothfels 2016). The Reactome pathway categorises reactions and subreactions into Reactome Events; CME was hierarchically organised into 21 sub-pathways (available at <https://reactome.org/PathwayBrowser/#/R-HSA-8856828>, accessed Oct 2021). The list of proteins involved for each Event were downloaded from the “Molecules” tab in the online viewer. The “MoleculeName” column includes the UniProt and HGNC symbols in one cell; the “Gene Name” portion was retained to match naming in 2A2-1.

Protein network

The online tool PINOT (v1.1, accessed Jan 2024) was used to acquire the interactors of the seed proteins, using the stringent filter in *Homo sapiens* (Tomkins et al. 2020). The binary protein-protein interactions of each query were obtained from all seven network providers. The output table was cleaned, with duplicate and self-edges removed. The table was divided for each Stage, creating the protein-protein interaction networks (PPINs) in table format (4.2). Cytoscape was used to visualise the PPINs (v3.9.1), via the API RCy3 (2.18.0) (Shannon et al. 2003; Gustavsen et al. 2019). The PPINs were constructed, first with all the first-layer PPIs (3.4), and then with only seed-seed interactions (3.8).

Clustering

Clustering algorithms were programmatically run for all stages with MCODE parameters ($a = 2$, $b = 0.1$, $c = 2$, $d = 100$), Haircut = T, where a) degree cutoff, b) node score cutoff, c) k-core, and d) maximum depth, respectively (Bader and Hogue 2003). Clusters with arranged by largest number of nodes, and unconnected nodes and clusters with $V < 3$ were removed.

Functional Enrichment Analysis

In order to identify local functions, gProfiler2 was used to query Biological Process (GO:BP), which returned the enrichment metric results (Kolberg et al. 2020). The term names were reannotated using rrvgo, using the distance method calculation “Resnik” and a threshold of 0.6.

Gene expression analysis

GTEX was queried for RNA expression levels (read counts) in 12 tissue sites: Amygdala, Caudate (basal ganglia), Cerebellum, Frontal Cortex (BA9), Hippocampus, Hypothalamus, Nucleus Accumbens, Pituitary, Putamen, Spinal Cord (C1), Substantia Nigra, and Tibial Nerve. Data for the 11 brain regions were accessed on 6 Sept 2024, with tibial nerve accessed on 18 Sept 2025 (all GTEX V8) (Consortium 2013). All 12 regions were accessed on 13 Jan 2025 for ND investigation (GTEX V10). Expression data were acquired for the CME seed list using their HGNC symbols. Samples quality control (QC) was performed via hierarchical clustering for each tissue expression set.

Weighted Gene Co-expression Network Analysis (WGCNA)

Within HPC, get expression levels in 12 brain regions for seed list. WGCNA - soft power selection, dendrogram with co-expressed modules. WGCNA was performed using the WGCNA R package. Soft-thresholding power was selected based on scale-free topology criteria, and networks were constructed using a signed/unsigned adjacency matrix. Modules were detected using dynamic tree cutting, with TOM used to refine module structure. Module eigengenes were correlated with tissues to identify tissue-specific modules.

Pair-wise Differential Expression Analysis (DEA)

Pair-wise Differential Expression Analysis (DEA) was performed to compare the expression values of CME genes across 12 tissues via the R package “DESeq2” (Love *et al*, 2014). In “DESeq2”, p-values generated during each round of DEA between every pair of tissues were automatically adjusted for multiple testing correction. These p-values were further corrected using Bonferroni’s method. This resulted in a matrix containing DEA p-values for each possible pair of tissues, for all LRRK2 interactors. For each interactor, tissues were ranked according to the DEA results via the following method: for interactor I , if its expression level in Tissue A is significantly higher than in Tissue B (Bonferroni corrected p-value < 0.05), then $Score_{I,A}^{Ex} = Score_{I,A}^{Ex} + 1$, while $Score_{I,B}^{Ex}$ remains unchanged, and vice versa. If the comparison between Tissue A and Tissue B is insignificant (Bonferroni corrected p-value ≥ 0.05), both $Score_{I,A}^{Ex}$ and $Score_{I,B}^{Ex}$ remain unchanged. According to this classification, for interactor I , $Score_{I,A}^{Ex}$ was directly indicative of the expression level of interactor I in Tissue A in comparison with the other tissues: the higher the $Score_{I,A}^{Ex}$, the higher the expression of interactor I in Tissue A. Interactors that presented uniquely and significantly high expression in certain tissues ($Score_{I,A}^{Ex} \geq 12$), meaning that the expression level of Interactor I in Tissue A is higher than 85.7% (12/14) tissues.

A heatmap was generated based on the mean expression values of CME genes in different tissues calculated from the normalised read counts matrix generated via the the R package “DESeq2”. Hierarchical clustering across CME genes and tissues were performed simultaneously.

Neurodegenerative (ND) gene identification

The conservative approach employed in this project utilises only Mendelian-inheritance genes in disease. The Genomics England resource PanelApp was selected as the source for the ND seed list as it categorises NDs on a scale of disease-causing and is used as a diagnostic resource by the NHS (<https://panelapp.genomicsengland.co.uk>). The full list was downloaded from Panel R58 v2.178, accessed Oct 2021) (Martin *et al*. 2019). The ND seed list was filtered to retain only green or amber annotated genes. The gene names were standardised using the HGNC symbols.

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Figure Legends

Figure 1 – Identification and categorisation of the core machinery of CME (A) simplified staging framework for CME (B) Categorisation of seed proteins derived from the Reactome resource (C) Summary of distribution of CME seeds across the stages, indicating seeds unique to one stage, and those shared across multiple stages.

Figure 2 – The protein interactome topography of CME. Seeds and interactors are indicated by pink (●) and blue (●) nodes. Edges indicate protein-protein interactions.

Figure 3 – (A) Node Distribution Histogram for the CME network - bin = 1 degree (B) Distribution of protein degree and betweenness centrality for seeds (magenta) and interactors. (C) Interactors ranked in descending degree, including bridge protein analysis and degree distribution in the full PPIN. The top ten non-seed bridge proteins are indicated in the accompanying table

Figure 4 – Identification of stage specific interactions; seed-seed interaction for all five CME Stages, with central proteins represented as a single node “ALL”.

Figure 5 – (A) Summary of clusters for each stage, arranged according to the designated stages of the CME process. (B) Count of number of proteins in final cluster for all five Stages. Full clusters summary in supplemental tables 2 and 3.

Figure 6 – Detailed cluster maps for all stages (A) Stage 1 clustered PPIN with only seed proteins and seed-seed interactions retained. The MCODE cluster algorithm was applied with settings defined in Section 2C3. Three clusters formed in Stage 1: S1C1, S1C2, and S1C3. (B) Stage 2 clustered PPIN with only seed-seed interactions retained. MCODE cluster algorithm applied with settings as defined in Section 2C3. Clusters formed: S2C1, S2C2, and Stage 2 Cluster 3 (S2C3). (C) Stage 3 clustered PPIN with only seed-seed interaction. MCODE cluster algorithm applied with settings as defined in Section 2C3. Clusters formed: S3C1, S3C2, and Stage 3 Cluster 3 (S3C3). (D) Stage 4/5 clustered PPIN with only seed-seed interaction. MCODE cluster algorithm applied with settings as defined in Section 2C3. Clusters formed: S4C1, S4C2, and Stage 4 Cluster 3 (S4C3). Key: Node colour indicates the number of Stages in which each protein is involved, ranging from one (●) to five (●). Node shape is used to denote the MCODE seed protein, represented as a square (■). Edge colour reflects the Final Score (Fs), with lighter grey edges representing lower values and darker grey indicating higher scores. The edge stroke style also represents Final Score, using dotted lines for $F_s < 3$, and solid lines where $F_s \geq 3$. Edge width corresponds to Edge Betweenness, from lowest (thin lines) to highest (thick lines) values.

Figure 7 – Ontological analysis of CME clusters by stage, highlighting enriched cellular processes for each stage.

Figure 8 – (A) Dendrogram with co-expression modules for 132/143 of the CME seed proteins in twelve tissue sites: Amygdala, Caudate (basal ganglia), Cerebellum, Frontal Cortex (BA9), Hippocampus, Hypothalamus, Nucleus Accumbens, Pituitary, Putamen, Spinal Cord (C1), Substantia Nigra, and Tibial Nerve (RNA-seq data acquired from GTEx). The dendrogram shows hierarchically clustered seed proteins using the WGCNA dissimilarity matrix. There was only one module identified in both the preliminary (unmerged) and final (merged) module detection passes. This

module is shown in turquoise tME, contained thirty proteins, and represents the co-expression module (module eigengene). (B) Heatmap of module-trait correlation analysis for the only module eigengene (ME) identified through Weighted Gene Co-expression Network Analysis (WGCNA). RNA-seq data from 132 genes across the twelve tissues were acquired from the GTEx consortium portal. Key: Colours indicate the direction and strength of the module-trait correlation. Deeper red signifies stronger positive correlation with a tissue, while deeper blue shows a stronger negative correlation. The ME was positively correlated with the frontal cortex (BA9) ($r = 0.288$), indicating that the thirty proteins in the ME were highly co-expressed in this brain region. (C) Heatmap illustrating differential gene expression (DGE) across eleven brain regions and the tibial nerve, using RNA-seq data acquired from GTEx. Key: Rows represent individual genes, and columns are the twelve tissue regions. Dendrograms on the x and y axes indicate hierarchical clustering of tissues and genes respectively, based on their expression patterns. Colour: expression values were transformed to a colour scale with values normalised across tissues for each gene; deeper shades of red indicate higher expression. There were 30 genes that comprised the turquoise module eigengene (tME), as identified in the previous WGCNA. These are indicated in turquoise for each gene (■).

Figure 9 – Neurodegenerative disease seed proteins following quality control, with ring chart divisions. (A) A ring chart key depicting clinical annotation colour mapping using the ND Disease Matrix (DM). An example ND seed, MAPT, is shown to provide a key for node properties; node visualised in Cytoscape. MAPT has 9 phenotypes in PanelApp, with each semantically classified using clinical annotations. The new annotations distributed the phenotypes into four clinical ND groups: Dementia, Nieman-Pick Disease, Parkinson’s Disease, and Other. These were proportionally represented as ring chart on each ND node using the DM. The overlap between neurodegenerative disease seeds and CME stages (B) Stage 1 ND-CME seed PPIN (C) Stage 2 ND-CME seed PPIN (D) Stage 3 ND-CME seed PPIN (E) Stage 4 ND-CME seed PPIN (F) Stage 5 ND-CME seed PPIN.

Figure 10 – Expression analysis of neurodegenerative diseases CME networks (A) Dendrogram with co-expression modules CME and ND proteins in twelve tissue sites: Amygdala, Caudate (basal ganglia), Cerebellum, Frontal Cortex (BA9), Hippocampus, Hypothalamus, Nucleus Accumbens, Pituitary, Putamen, Spinal Cord (C1), Substantia Nigra, and Tibial Nerve. RNA-seq data acquired from GTEx. The dendrogram shows hierarchically clustered seed proteins using the WGCNA dissimilarity matrix. There were four modules identified in both the preliminary (unmerged) and final (merged) module detection passes. There were 118 ungrouped proteins (■), with the modules shown as coloured. The pink module eigengene (pME) (■) contained 65 proteins, blue module eigengene (bME) (■) contained 47 proteins, sienna module eigengene (sME) (■) contained 28 proteins, and yellow module eigengene (yME) (■) contained 26 proteins. These represent the co-expression module (module eigengene). (B) Heatmap illustrating differential gene expression (DGE) across eleven brain regions and the tibial nerve, using RNA-seq data acquired from GTEx. Key: Rows represent individual genes, and columns are the twelve tissue regions. Dendrograms on the x and y axes indicate hierarchical clustering of tissues and genes respectively, based on their expression patterns. Colour: expression values were transformed to a colour scale with values normalised across tissues for each gene; deeper shades of red indicate higher expression.

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References

- Bader, G. D., & Hogue, C. W. (2003). An automated method for finding molecular complexes in large protein interaction networks. *BMC Bioinformatics*, 4, 2, doi:10.1186/1471-2105-4-2.
- Bhore, N., Bogacki, E. C., O'Callaghan, B., Plun-Favreau, H., Lewis, P. A., & Herbst, S. (2024). Common genetic risk for Parkinson's disease and dysfunction of the endo-lysosomal system. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci*, 379(1899), 20220517, doi:10.1098/rstb.2022.0517.
- Consortium, G. T. (2013). The Genotype-Tissue Expression (GTEx) project. *Nat Genet*, 45(6), 580-585, doi:10.1038/ng.2653.
- Croft, D., O'Kelly, G., Wu, G., Haw, R., Gillespie, M., Matthews, L., et al. (2011). Reactome: a database of reactions, pathways and biological processes. *Nucleic Acids Res*, 39(Database issue), D691-697, doi:10.1093/nar/gkq1018.
- Doherty, G. J., & McMahon, H. T. (2009). Mechanisms of endocytosis. *Annu Rev Biochem*, 78, 857-902, doi:10.1146/annurev.biochem.78.081307.110540.
- Fabregat, A., Jupe, S., Matthews, L., Sidiropoulos, K., Gillespie, M., Garapati, P., et al. (2018). The Reactome Pathway Knowledgebase. *Nucleic Acids Res*, 46(D1), D649-D655, doi:10.1093/nar/gkx1132.
- Gillespie, M., Jassal, B., Stephan, R., Milacic, M., Rothfels, K., Senff-Ribeiro, A., et al. (2022). The reactome pathway knowledgebase 2022. *Nucleic Acids Res*, 50(D1), D687-D692, doi:10.1093/nar/gkab1028.
- Gustavsen, J. A., Pai, S., Isserlin, R., Demchak, B., & Pico, A. R. (2019). RCy3: Network biology using Cytoscape from within R. *F1000Res*, 8, 1774, doi:10.12688/f1000research.20887.3.
- Kaci, A. H., S.; Manzoni, C.; Lewis, P.A. (2026). Clathrin Mediated Endocytosis as an axis for the etiopathogenesis of Parkinson's disease. *Journal of Cell Science*, *In press*.
- Kaksonen, M., & Roux, A. (2018). Mechanisms of clathrin-mediated endocytosis. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol*, 19(5), 313-326, doi:10.1038/nrm.2017.132.
- Kolberg, L., Raudvere, U., Kuzmin, I., Vilo, J., & Peterson, H. (2020). gprofiler2 -- an R package for gene list functional enrichment analysis and namespace conversion toolset g:Profiler. *F1000Res*, 9, doi:10.12688/f1000research.24956.2.
- Liu, Y., Beyer, A., & Aebersold, R. (2016). On the Dependency of Cellular Protein Levels on mRNA Abundance. *Cell*, 165(3), 535-550, doi:10.1016/j.cell.2016.03.014.
- Love, M. I., Huber, W., & Anders, S. (2014). Moderated estimation of fold change and dispersion for RNA-seq data with DESeq2. *Genome Biol*, 15(12), 550, doi:10.1186/s13059-014-0550-8.
- Martin, A. R., Williams, E., Foulger, R. E., Leigh, S., Daugherty, L. C., Niblock, O., et al. (2019). PanelApp crowdsources expert knowledge to establish consensus diagnostic gene panels. *Nat Genet*, 51(11), 1560-1565, doi:10.1038/s41588-019-0528-2.
- Clathrin-mediated endocytosis (2016).
- Schulze-Niemand, E., & Naumann, M. (2023). The COP9 signalosome: A versatile regulatory hub of Cullin-RING ligases. *Trends Biochem Sci*, 48(1), 82-95, doi:10.1016/j.tibs.2022.08.003.
- Shannon, P., Markiel, A., Ozier, O., Baliga, N. S., Wang, J. T., Ramage, D., et al. (2003). Cytoscape: a software environment for integrated models of

- biomolecular interaction networks. *Genome Res*, 13(11), 2498-2504, doi:10.1101/gr.1239303.
- Tomkins, J. E., Ferrari, R., Vavouraki, N., Hardy, J., Lovering, R. C., Lewis, P. A., et al. (2020). PINOT: an intuitive resource for integrating protein-protein interactions. *Cell Commun Signal*, 18(1), 92, doi:10.1186/s12964-020-00554-5.
- Varusai, T. M., Jupe, S., Sevilla, C., Matthews, L., Gillespie, M., Stein, L., et al. (2021). Using Reactome to build an autophagy mechanism knowledgebase. *Autophagy*, 17(6), 1543-1554, doi:10.1080/15548627.2020.1761659.

Figure 2

Figure 4

B

CME Stage	Clusters (C)	C1	C2	C3	Total
Stage 1	3	18	6	6	30
Stage 2	3	8	6	6	20
Stage 3	3	14	9	4	27
Stage 4	3	12	9	6	27
Stage 5	3	12	9	6	27

Figure 5

A

B

C

D

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10